

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF TECHNOLOGIES SOLAR POWER PLANT AND WIND POWER PLANT.

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Annotation. The use of solar and wind energy contributes to an increase in the share of inexhaustible energy sources to cover the energy needs of the world. More than 100 countries have already formulated policy goals for expanding the use of renewable energy sources and have introduced corresponding energy programs that oblige grid operators to buy electricity produced by renewable energy sources. According to scientists, the age of the Sun is about 4.5 billion years and, according to the classification of stars, it can remain unchanged for another 5 billion years. Its energy potential is so huge. If we compare the radiation power of one square meter of the solar surface, then the closest analogy is the amount of current consumed by a million classic filament lamps. Therefore, the energy of the Sun can become an inexhaustible stream, which in terms of power many times exceeds the entire volume of electricity generated throughout the world. It remains to find the most efficient and cost-effective way to use this resource.

Key words: Advantages, limitations, high price, long payback period, noiseless operation, Expensive batteries.

However, in order to study the energy potential of solar radiation and wind power, in order to most effectively use SES / WES technologies and, as a result, increase electricity production with its subsequent sale at a "green" tariff, it is

necessary to involve energy industry specialists. In accordance with the Law of Ukraine "On the Electric Power Industry", unlike industrial SPPs with a capacity of more than 30 kW, the following additional incentives are provided for owners of private SPPs and / or WPPs: the production of electricity from wind energy and solar radiation of a private household is carried out without an appropriate license; the size of the "green" tariff is tied to the euro exchange rate (with an increase in the euro exchange rate, the tariff also increases).

Advantages and disadvantages of technologies Solar power plant :

- noiselessness of work;
- the service life of solar cells is practically unlimited and can be tens of years;
- the conversion of solar energy occurs mainly through the use of photovoltaic cells;
- additional or autonomous source of electricity in a private house;
- the possibility of obtaining a "green" tariff.

Disadvantages of ses technology:

- dependence on the climatic characteristics of the area;
- need for a large area.

Wps technology advantages:

- wind energy is inexhaustible; the production of electricity using wind farms is not accompanied by hazardous emissions into the atmosphere;
- the possibility of placement in hard-to-reach places;

- require a small area and fit into any landscape; obtaining free electricity in the long term, no costs for fuel and its delivery;
- autonomy - independence from the state and operation of external electrical networks.

Disadvantages of wes:

- noise;
- high price;
- long payback period;
- volatility and unregulated wind flow.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

In recent years, in many countries of the world, scientists have paid close attention to the development of power plants that use environmentally friendly "green" energy. And the most powerful and most accessible source of alternative energy is the Sun. Scientific developments and modern technologies have reached a high level. Solar energy is currently used to provide power to artificial space objects, satellites and manned space stations in Earth orbit, interplanetary research probes. And this is not the limit. Thanks to innovative technologies, the emergence of new materials, it has become possible to build solar power plants that are designed for autonomous power supply.

Private residential buildings remote from the centralized power lines of objects, commercial and industrial buildings of different power consumption. And

although the advantages and disadvantages of solar power plants are still discussed in the professional field, in practice it turns out that installing a solar power plant is a cost-effective solution. Indeed, in this case, to obtain electricity, it is not required to bring fuel, connect to the central power grid. Electricity from a solar power plant is generated almost all year round without regard to global crises and political collapses.

Starting to consider the pros and cons of solar power plants, you need to familiarize yourself with certain information regarding solar energy. On a fine day, with a clear sky, 1 kilowatt of solar energy falls on 1 square meter of the earth's surface. A modern model of a photovoltaic module of equal area can generate 170 watts of electricity. Accordingly, the efficiency of such a solar battery is 17.0%. Even with such a relatively low productivity, solar power plants are popular not only among companies, organizations, other forms of legal entities, but also among ordinary citizens. This is due to the stability, independence and short payback period of investments. To verify this, you need to consider in detail what solar power plants have advantages and disadvantages.

III. CONCLUSION.

With all these advantages, there are also disadvantages of solar energy, which are quite easily solved:

- The performance of solar panels depends on the time of day and the weather. At night, in the absence of sunlight, photovoltaic modules do not generate electricity. A cloudy sky significantly reduces the level of generation. But the installation of batteries solves the problem of providing electricity to the facility served by the solar power plant.
- High price. This is a minus, but relative. Despite the fact that the installation of a solar power plant is quite an expensive undertaking, such an investment justifies itself. Firstly, this is a one-time investment, which immediately begins to pay for itself from the moment it is put into operation. Secondly, the

development of science and technology every year makes solar power plants more affordable.

- Periodic maintenance. Despite the automation of the station, its equipment needs maintenance. To ensure that the efficiency of solar panels does not decrease, they must be cleaned of dust and dirt, and snow should be swept off them in winter. But these are periodic events that do not take much time and do not require significant labor costs.
- Large areas are required for the installation of solar panels. This problem is solved by installing panels on roofs, wastelands and even on walls. In addition, smaller and more efficient models of photovoltaic modules are being developed.
- Expensive batteries. Today, the battery issue is being addressed by many global brands involved in the development and production of electric vehicles. There is a prospect of obtaining in the near future inexpensive, but very capacious batteries capable of maintaining a charge for a long time.

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